

ANALYSIS OF SOCIAL INTERACTION IN EFFORTS TO ACHIEVE CLEAN GOVERNMENT IN THE 2024 LEGISLATIVE ELECTIONS IN BANDUNG CITY

Dewi Kurniasih¹, Tris Dina Susanti², Yusuf Adam Hilman³, Ferdi Ramdana⁴

¹Universitas Komputer Indonesia, ²Universitas Majalengka,
³Universitas Muhammadiyah Ponorogo

dewi.kurniasih@email.unikom.ac.id

ABSTRACT

This study was motivated by the condition of the election organizing body in its efforts to achieve Clean Government as seen from five indicators, namely: participation, transparency, accountability, effectiveness, and law enforcement. These conditions were analysed using social interaction theory in the form of cooperation, competition, accommodation, and conflict. This study used a qualitative approach combined with a descriptive strategy. Data collection techniques include literature review, observation, and in-depth interviews. The researcher used purposive sampling to identify informants. Data analysis was conducted qualitatively through the stages of data collection, data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion. The results of the study indicate that the city of Bandung has made various efforts to improve good governance, reduce corruption, and increase public trust in the city government. Social interaction among Bandung residents during the legislative elections was generally conducive. Bandung residents showed good participation, including first-time voters with an increase in their participation rates.

Keywords: Social Interaction, Clean Government, Legislative Elections.

Introduction

Democracy gives rise to general elections as its manifestation, which is enshrined in the constitution. Law No. 7 of 2017 on General Elections explains that elections are a process of people's sovereignty, which must be carried out through direct, public, free, confidential, honest, and fair voting (Kurniasih, 2012).

In line with the spirit of the general election, in the implementation of these activities, it is necessary to emphasise the government organisations in charge of carrying out their obligations professionally and well, providing maximum service, and being able to receive aspirations and complaints coming from users.

In addition to preparations in terms of organising elections professionally, it is also necessary to identify related conditions in the field, as a form of mitigation in preparing for the possibilities that can occur, as a measurable effort that must be maximised.

The election in 2024 aims to elect new members of parliament as well as the president and vice president. The 2024 General Election Permanent Voter List (DPT) totalled 204,807,222 people, according to the KPU website, an increase compared to the 2019 election of 192.83 million registered voters (databooks.katadata.co.id, 2019).

Compared to previous editions of the election, which were usually held close to polling day, or what is commonly referred to as 'dawn strikes', the practice of vote buying is predicted to become commonplace in the 2024 election. Transactional politics can occur 'person to person', and also between groups. This can be done by legislative candidates and success teams representing neighbourhoods, villages/hamlets, even villages, as well as regional representatives. Youth organisations, religious organisations, and other community groups may also have similar problems. And perhaps the amount we are discussing now is millions of rupiah, not just Rp. 20,000 to Rp. 100,000 for a group of individuals.

The second issue that can arise is identity politics, where political actors use ethnic groups, tribes, cultures, religions, as a political tactic for various reasons, such as the display of mainstream or opposition group identification. Here, identity is mobilised through radical interpretations to win over voters who identify as 'the same' in terms of race, ethnicity, religion or other similarities.

Ideally, the implementation of elections must fulfil 11 principles, namely: independence, integrity, justice, legal certainty, order, and openness, as stated in the regulations, but in reality BAWASLU noted that in 2019, there were more than 7,598 reports of violations that had been investigated and ignored as violations.

We identified these conditions into several assumptions, including: 1). the weakness of participatory monitoring mechanisms in Bandung City. Although there are regulations and election supervisory institutions, the capacity and independence of supervisory institutions are often questioned. Limited resources, both in terms of human resource capacity and infrastructure support, are a significant obstacle in realising comprehensive supervision. 2). the complexity of power relations between various political actors that have the potential to affect the neutrality of the monitoring process. Partisan interests, power networks, and socio-political capital often create distortions in election monitoring mechanisms. Unbalanced social interactions can result in biased and unobjective surveillance practices. 3). low public participation in election monitoring. Limited knowledge, apathy, and lack of space for real participation cause the people of Bandung City to tend to be passive objects in the democratic process, not active subjects who are able to oversee the integrity of elections. 4). cultural challenges in building a transparent oversight culture. The legacy of a centralised and hierarchical bureaucratic culture often hinders the creation of participatory and dialogical oversight mechanisms. Social interaction patterns that are still vertical and subordinate are an obstacle in realising clean government.

This research seeks to fill the academic and practical gap in understanding the dynamics of social interaction in the election monitoring process. With a sociological

perspective, this study does not merely describe the phenomenon, but analyses the hidden mechanisms that affect the quality of local democracy. The significance of the research lies in its contribution to developing an election monitoring model based on social interaction that is more responsive, participatory, and has integrity. The research findings are expected to be a reference for policy makers, election supervisory institutions, and stakeholders in designing more effective supervision strategies. Through an in-depth analysis of social interaction in the implementation of clean government, this research contributes to systematic efforts to strengthen the quality of democracy at the local level, especially in Bandung City.

The novelty in this research uses a comprehensive sociological perspective in studying the 2024 elections, focusing on the dynamics of social interactions that go beyond conventional procedural and administrative-based approaches. This research breaks through the boundaries of traditional studies by exploring the network of power relations, construction of meaning, and social practices hidden in the process of monitoring the legislative elections. Through in-depth analyses of the interactions between actors - including election organisers, civil society, the media and other stakeholders - this study seeks to uncover hidden mechanisms that affect the quality of local democracy. The sociological approach used does not merely describe phenomena, but rather interprets the complexity of social relations, cultural values, and power dynamics that shape election monitoring practices in Bandung City.

The urgency of this research lies in the complexity of local democratisation challenges, where the 2024 Legislative Election is a critical moment in Indonesia's democratisation process that demands responsive and participatory supervision models to prevent potential conflicts and manipulations in the electoral process. The need for institutional transformation is imperative in the face of increasingly complex contemporary political dynamics, which requires innovation in election monitoring mechanisms to build public trust in the democratic process. Furthermore, this research is a critical response to the crisis of trust characterised by declining public participation in the electoral process, which indicates the urgent need for a new approach in building democratic integrity. Through systematic efforts to encourage active community involvement in monitoring, this study seeks to transform the paradigm of election monitoring from merely procedural to participatory, dialogical and meaningful. Thus, this study does not merely offer academic analysis, but also contributes to the reconstruction of a more inclusive, transparent and civilised democratisation practice at the local level.

Table 1 Prior Studies

<p><i>Rusfiana & Kurniasih (2024)</i> with the title <i>The Role of Civil Society Organizations in Promoting Social and Political Change in Indonesia</i> with the research results that reveal the complexity of social interaction dynamics in the implementation of clean government in the 2024 Legislative Election in Bandung City through a series of fundamental findings. The research identifies that the election monitoring process is</p>
--

not simply a matter of procedural mechanisms, but a complex network of social relations between various political actors, bureaucracy, civil society, and the media.

Second, Andrew, Altje, & Hera Rotulung (2022) with the title Political Communication Phenomena in Community Social Interaction, the results of the study explored three fundamental dimensions of motivation that shape voters' decisions, namely past motives built on historical experiences, future motives related to projections of collective hopes and ideals, and present motives that represent the actual conditions and immediate needs of the community.

The research findings reveal the complexity of Instagram's role in the dynamics of contemporary political opinion formation, by identifying fundamental mechanisms that contribute to the polarisation of people's perspectives. This social media platform is shown to have significant power in shaping the construction of political viewpoints through a series of complex mechanisms, including sophisticated algorithms that selectively curate content, create echo chamber effects that reinforce existing beliefs, and networks of political influencers that have the capacity to mobilise public opinion. The research insightfully highlights how engaging and strategic visual content on Instagram is able to evoke intense emotional responses, which in turn further reinforce polarised attitudes. This psychological mechanism operates through visual stimulation designed to mobilise viewers' affections and emotional identification with particular political narratives. The significance of the research lies in its comprehensive understanding of the dynamics of social media interaction in the contemporary political landscape, particularly in the context of elections. The research does not merely describe phenomena, but rather explores the hidden mechanisms that shape the construction of public opinion in the digital space.

This research has its own characteristics in exploring social interactions in the monitoring of the 2024 Legislative Elections in Bandung City, which show both similarities and significant differences with previous studies. Methodologically, this research is in line with previous studies in using an interpretative qualitative approach, a focus on in-depth analysis, and attention to the complexity of relationships between actors in the democratic process, but the difference is the comprehensive sociological perspective used, the specific research locus in Bandung City, and the specific focus on the supervision of the 2024 Legislative Elections. Having a diversity of theoretical perspectives ranging from the role of civil society organisations, voter motivation, to the role of social media in the formation of political opinions, this research offers a unique contribution in the form of an in-depth model of social interaction analysis and a comprehensive understanding of the dynamics of clean government at the local level, thus filling an academic gap through an innovative and contextual approach.

From this background, we would like to research by taking the title: 'Analysis Of Social Interaction In Efforts To Achieve Clean Government In The 2024 Legislative Elections In Bandung City'.

METHOD

This research combines a qualitative approach with descriptive methodology. The research location was carried out in the city of Bandung, especially at the General Election Supervisory Agency which is located at Jl. Nuansa Mas Raya No.2, Cipamokolan, Rancasari, Bandung City, the General Election Commission which is located at Jl. Soekarno Hatta No. 260, Buahbatu Bandung, Bandung. The time of this research was carried out from March to August 2024.

Data used in the form of primary and secondary data, for the interview data is determined through purposive sampling method, which determines the informant with the consideration that the informant understands the election issues, the data that has been collected is then tested for validity through in-depth observation, and triangulation.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Accountability and transparency of regional government emerge from the Regional Government Implementation Report (LPPD) and the Accountability Information Report (LKPJ) to fulfill the aspects of accountability and transparency of government communicated to the public. In addition, the participation of public aspirations is also seen in the number of voters in the general election (Pemilu). In addition to the supremacy of law, the concept of a state of law includes two fundamental principles. The main objective is to stop people in authority from abusing their influence. Second, it aims to protect society by ensuring that individuals do not engage in activities that are outside the scope of the law and can cause chaos or disorder. This will allow people to exercise their rights without violating legal restrictions.

Social Interactions in the Implementation of Clean Government during the 2024 Legislative General Election in Bandung City in the Aspects of Transparency and Accountability

Transparency is one of the key elements in realizing clean governance. This includes providing information to the public at all stages of the election, including: The process of registering voters and candidates for parliament. Management of campaign funds by candidates and political parties. Monitoring and announcing election results publicly in real time. Public Access to Financial Reports Related to General Election Activities.

Responsibility for Election Supervision Accountability refers to the requirement that organizations tasked with organizing elections, including the Election Supervisory Body (Bawaslu) and the KPU (General Election Commission), provide

transparent and accountable reports to the public on how the election was held in an orderly manner.

Effective and easily accessible reporting mechanisms for violations by the public. Participatory monitoring of citizens, the media and civil society organizations in monitoring fraud and violations in election campaigns and voting. A clear process for resolving election disputes and investigating fraud.

The role of technology in increasing transparency and accountability on using of digital technology, such as electronic voting systems, the official website of the KPU (General Election Commission) which provides real-time data, and online complaint platforms, supports the achievement of transparency. In addition, social media can be a tool to directly monitor and report violations committed by the community.

The people of Bandung City can report through Bawaslu by visiting the secretariat or through the sapawarga application channel. Which is actually a concrete manifestation of social interaction in the 2024 Legislative Election supervision system. This reporting mechanism is not just an administrative procedure, but a representation of the dynamics of social relations between the community and the supervisory institution, where every citizen is placed as an active subject in maintaining the integrity of the democratic process.

The sapawarga application is a strategic instrument in transforming traditional social interaction patterns into digital spaces that allow for broader, more inclusive, and responsive participation. Through this digital platform, the people of Bandung are no longer just objects of supervision, but active partners in realizing clean government. Each report submitted forms a complex communication network, where information flows interactively between the community, Bawaslu, and other stakeholders.

The multiple choices between reporting directly to the secretariat or through the sapawarga application reflect the flexibility of social interaction in the context of election supervision. For people who are more familiar with conventional mechanisms, coming directly to the secretariat is an option that provides a personal and meaningful interaction experience. Meanwhile, for the digital generation, the sapawarga application offers convenience, speed, and wider reach in conveying aspirations and findings during the election process.

This reporting system fundamentally changes the power relations between the community and the supervisory institution. The community is no longer treated as a passive subject, but has an equal position in overseeing the democratic process. Each report becomes a potential transformation, where the information submitted can trigger investigations, corrections, or improvements in the general election system.

In a theoretical context, the reporting mechanism through Bawaslu and sapawarga can be understood as a democratic deliberation space, where every citizen has the opportunity to participate, express their observations, and contribute to

maintaining the integrity of the political process. Social interaction does not stop at submitting reports, but continues in the process of follow-up, verification, and potential resolution involving various social actors.

Thus, both through the secretariat and the sapawarga application, the reporting mechanism of the Bandung City community in the supervision of the 2024 Legislative Election shows that clean government is not an abstract concept, but rather a concrete social practice that requires active participation, transparency, and joint commitment from all components of society.

Social Interactions in the Implementation of Clean Government during the 2024 Legislative General Election in Bandung City in the Aspect of Community Participation

Public participation varies due to factors such as culture, education, awareness, and government policies. The public can report corruption or unethical practices, helping to identify problems and necessary actions. Information about government policies, programs, and projects should be clear and easily accessible to the public, through websites, publications, brochures, and other media. Public participation can also be seen from the existence of elections. In the context of supervising the 2024 elections in Bandung City, it is important to consider the implementation of clean governance by emphasizing the aspect of public participation. Playing an active role in maintaining the integrity of the election process. Public participation is one of the key elements of a clean, transparent, and accountable election.

The following things can be considered. The importance of public participation in elections. Public participation is an active role of citizens. Up to supervision. The election community can help prevent and detect potential violations and create more transparent and accountable election conditions. In the context of clean governance, this participation is also a form of public participation in a clean and open democratic process.

Forms of Community Participation, Community participation in the Monitoring of the 2024 Bandung City Election can take various forms, including. Voter Participation. Community Participation by Visiting Please come to your polling station and vote honestly and according to procedure. Direct Supervision on the Spot. Members of the community can act as volunteer election monitors as part of non-governmental organizations (NGOs) or community groups that monitor the election process, voting, and voting can be counting.

Reporting Violations Citizens have the opportunity to report any violations or suspected irregularities during the election through the online platform provided by Bawaslu or directly to the relevant authorities. Dissemination of Information Citizens have a role in disseminating information about the importance of clean elections and educating other citizens about the dangers of voting procedures and monetary policy.

The role of civil society organizations, Civil society organizations (NGOs) play an important role in encouraging and increasing community participation. In Bandung City, many non-governmental organizations focus on election monitoring and interaction. Non-governmental organizations often train election monitor volunteers and lobby to ensure that the election process is carried out in accordance with democratic standards. They are also involved in anti-money laundering and election fraud campaigns as part of public education.

Social Interactions in the Implementation of Clean Government during the 2024 Legislative General Election in Bandung City in the Aspect of the Supremacy of Law

The condition of law enforcement in the city of Bandung is good, it's just that there are still many officials who are not aware of their duties and obligations which have led to several abuses of power. The ideals of accountability, transparency, and good governance can be legally implemented through the establishment of a clear and strong legislative framework regarding clean government. This regulation must provide strict sanctions for violations of the principle of clean government.

Here are some important points that can be considered in the context of the supremacy of law in monitoring the 2024 Election in the City of Bandung:

1. Defining the supremacy of law in a clean government The Supremacy Law means that all actions of the state, institutions, and citizens are under the supervision of the law without exception. In the context of elections, the supremacy of law guarantees that the entire election process runs according to applicable law and no political party is immune from the law. By emphasizing the supremacy of law, "clean government" means that all forms of fraud, manipulation, and election fraud are subject to sanctions in accordance with applicable legal provisions.

2. Legal Framework for Elections in Indonesia The Election Law (Law Number 7 of 2017 concerning Elections) is the main legal basis for organizing elections in Indonesia, including the City of Bandung. This law regulates various aspects ranging from voter registration to election campaigns and the vote counting process. The Election Supervisory Body, or Bawaslu, is an organization tasked with overseeing the implementation of elections and ensuring that each stage is carried out in accordance with legal requirements. The law clearly provides legal sanctions for election violations, including monetary policy actions, election manipulation, intimidation, and campaign violations.
3. The Role of Bawaslu and Legal Institutions in Election Supervision Bawaslu plays an important role in maintaining the supremacy of law in election supervision in the City of Bandung. Bawaslu must ensure that reported violations are handled in accordance with the law. A number of law enforcement officers, including the police and prosecutors, work together with Bawaslu to handle incidents of legal violations that occur during the election, including processing reports of violations received. The Gakumdu Center (Integrated Law Enforcement

Agency) consisting of Bawasul, Pori, and the Prosecutor's Office also plays a role in the fast and accurate process of election crimes.

4. Election Violations and Law Enforcement Potential violations can occur in the implementation of the 2024 Election. Financial policies where candidates or political parties try to influence voters through material rewards. Abuse of power by public officials or government officials to obtain certain candidates. Intimidation of voters or election witnesses, especially in certain areas that have a history of conflict or strong political influence. Manipulation of voting results during vote counting at the TPS or regional KPU level.

The supremacy of law in the context of general elections is a fundamental principle that guarantees the upholding of justice, transparency, and integrity of the democratic process. In the complex landscape of the 2024 Legislative Election in Bandung City, the supremacy of law is not just an abstract concept, but a concrete practice that underlies every stage of political contestation. This principle emphasizes that no entity or individual is immune to the law, be it political parties, candidates, or election organizers.

The legal framework for elections in Indonesia, especially Law Number 7 of 2017, is the main foundation in realizing the supremacy of law. The law designs a comprehensive mechanism that regulates every aspect of the general election, from voter registration to the vote counting process. The General Election Supervisory Body (Bawaslu) plays a strategic role as a supervisory institution that ensures that every stage of the election runs according to applicable legal provisions.

The implementation of the supremacy of law in the supervision of the 2024 Legislative Election in the City of Bandung involves a complex network of law enforcement institutions. The Gakumdu Center (Integrated Law Enforcement Agency), consisting of Bawaslu, the National Police, and the Prosecutor's Office, is a key instrument in handling potential violations of the law. This collaboration between institutions allows for a quick and accurate response to any indication of election violations.

Potential election violations include a variety of complex political practices that have the potential to harm the integrity of democracy. Financial policies involving material transactions to influence voters, abuse of power by public officials, intimidation of voters or witnesses, and manipulation of vote counting results are some forms of threats to the principle of the supremacy of law.

The supremacy of law in the context of clean government requires a transparent, accountable, and fair oversight mechanism. Every violation must be handled professionally, objectively, and in accordance with applicable legal provisions. This is not just a matter of imposing sanctions, but a systematic effort to prevent the recurrence of practices that can damage the integrity of the democratic process.

The people of Bandung City have a strategic role in upholding the supremacy of law. Through the reporting mechanism at Bawaslu, either directly or through the sapawarga application, every citizen can actively contribute to overseeing the democratic process. Community participation is a key element in creating an effective and sustainable monitoring system. Thus, the supremacy of law in the 2024 Legislative Election in Bandung City is not just a process of enforcing rules, but a complex social practice. It demands a joint commitment from all actors to uphold the values of democracy, justice, and integrity in every stage of political contestation.

Social Interactions in the Implementation of Clean Government during the 2024 Legislative General Election in Bandung City in the Aspect of Social Interactions

Social processes are fundamental in understanding the dynamics of social interactions that occur in the supervision of the 2024 Legislative Election in Bandung City. According to Sukanto, social interaction is "social processes can be interpreted as ways of relating that can be seen when individuals and social groups meet each other and determine the system and forms of social relations." (Soekanto, 2017)

Based on the statement above, the statement about the social process describes the complexity of the dynamic interactions between actors involved in realizing a clean government, where individuals and social groups such as Bawaslu, KPU, legislative candidates, civil society, and voters do not simply interact procedurally, but form a meaningful social relationship system through communication mechanisms, negotiations, and symbolic exchanges. This process includes critical stages ranging from election socialization, voter registration, administrative verification, to supervision and resolution of potential conflicts, where each actor not only carries out its formal role, but also actively participates in creating a transparent, accountable, and dignified democratic space. Social interaction in the supervision of the Election is actually a complex social practice that goes beyond mere administrative procedures, but rather a dynamic construction in which the interests, perspectives, and democratic values of various parties negotiate, meet, and form an understanding in maintaining the integrity of the general election process, which in turn will determine the quality of local democracy in the City of Bandung.

The social process in the implementation of Clean Government is by providing a socialization carried out by the Bandung City General Election Commission based on the results of interviews with the Bandung City KPU Apparatus that the city of Bandung is supervising the 2024 Legislative Election through various coordinated and structured activities to ensure that the election runs honestly, fairly, and transparently.

According to Slamet Santosa, social interaction has the following characteristics:

"Social interaction is a dynamic system that requires the existence of relationships between individuals, awareness of goals, and compliance with social structures and functions that form the context of interaction." (Santosa, 2004)

In the context of the Implementation of Clean Government in the City of Bandung, social interactions display complex and dynamic systemic characteristics, where the relationship between individuals in the supervision of the 2024 Legislative Election is not merely a procedural mechanism, but a meaningful and intertwined social construction.

First, the relationship between individuals in the social interaction of election supervision in Bandung City is reflected through a complex network involving Bawaslu, KPU, legislative candidates, civil society, and voters. Each actor does not only play a formal role, but forms a system of interactions that are interconnected, influence each other, and control each other in realizing a dignified democratic process.

Awareness of the goal is a key element in this social interaction. Each actor brings a specific intentionality: Bawaslu aims to maintain the integrity of the election, KPU regulates the technical mechanism, legislative candidates fight for political representation, while civil society oversees transparency. These goals are not separate, but rather negotiate with each other and form a constellation of meaning in the local democratic process.

Social structures and functions act as a framework that shapes, limits, and enables social interactions in election supervision. Institutional structures, election regulations, complaint mechanisms, and democratic norms serve as guides at every stage of interaction. The social function of each actor is determined by their role and position in the democratic system, which simultaneously limits and provides space for participation.

Social interactions in the implementation of clean government in Bandung City are thus dynamic systems that are constantly moving, adapting, and mutating. It is not static, but rather responsive to changes in context, challenges, and the complexity of the democratic process. Every social interaction becomes a space where democratic values are practiced, tested, and reinterpreted.

Through this perspective, social interaction in the supervision of the 2024 Legislative Election in Bandung City is not merely an administrative procedure, but a complex social practice. It demands the ability of each actor to go beyond pragmatic interests, build trust, and commit to the principles of substantive democracy.

Thus, the characteristics of social interaction in the context of clean government lie in the ability of the social system to create a space for dialogue, negotiation, and participation that is inclusive, transparent, and dignified. Social interaction becomes a mechanism where democracy is not merely carried out, but experienced, interpreted, and presented as a living and sustainable social practice.

Conclusion

Social interaction in Community participation in election supervision in Bandung City showed a significant increase. Educational campaigns and community involvement in reporting violations succeeded in raising public awareness of the importance of active supervision. This participation reflects the increasing role of the community in maintaining the integrity of the election, although efforts are still needed to reach less involved groups. Transparency in the election supervision process in Bandung City has increased through the use of technology, such as online reporting applications and CCTV monitoring at polling stations. However, there are still several obstacles, especially related to the accessibility of information in certain areas and limited digital literacy among supervisors. Overall, transparency has helped increase public trust in the election process. Accountability in election supervision in Bandung City is reflected in the actions taken by supervisory institutions against identified violations. Institutions such as the Bandung City Bawaslu have made efforts to follow up on reports of violations with clear and open procedures. However, there are still challenges in terms of consistent enforcement of sanctions, especially in cases involving influential political actors. The effectiveness of election supervision in Bandung City can be seen from the decrease in the number of violations and the increase in the quality of election implementation. However, several weaknesses were still found in terms of coordination between supervisory institutions and limited infrastructure in several areas. In general, efforts to improve the effectiveness of supervision have shown positive results, although they still need to be improved.

One of the most difficult parts of implementing clean governance is law enforcement. The practice of money politics and ASN non-neutrality are problems that have not been fully resolved, despite major efforts to crack down on violations. Although strict and consistent law enforcement is essential to support clean governance, the application of penalties often faces a number of challenges.

Social interactions between actors in the supervision of the 2024 Legislative Election in Bandung City are formed through complex networks involving official institutions, civil society, and political stakeholders. Each actor plays a strategic role in maintaining the integrity of the democratic process, with ongoing communication, coordination, and mutual control mechanisms.

Reference

- Andrew, Y., Merentek, E. A., & Lotulung, L. J. H. (2020). Fenomena komunikasi politik dalam interaksi sosial masyarakat. *Acta Diurna Komunikasi Fenomena*, 4(1), 1-8.
- Diskominfo Kota Bandung. (2023, November 23). *Kota Bandung Komitmen Wujudkan Pemilu Kondusif, Tertib, Aman dan Santun*. Retrieved from PORTALJABARPROVGOID: <https://jabarprov.go.id/berita/kota-bandung-komitmen-wujudkan-pemilu-kondusif-tertib-aman-dan-santun-11445>
- Kurniasih, D. (2012). Pendidikan Politik Kader Partai Persatuan Pembangunan Pada

Persiapan Pemilihan Kepala Daerah Kota Cimahi Tahun 2012 Dewi Kurniasih.
Jurnal Teknologi Pendidikan, 1(2), 1-11.

Kurniasih, D., Ali, M., Amin, S., & Karniawati, N. (n.d.). *Penyusunan Roadmap Reformasi Birokrasi Dalam*. 3(1), 66-84.

Rusfiana, Y., & Kurniasih, D. (2024). The Role of Civil Society Organizations in Promoting Social and Political Change in Indonesia. *Journal of Ethnic and Cultural Studies*, 11(3), 187-207.

Santosa, P. (2008). *Administrasi Publik: Teori dan Aplikasi Good Governance*. Bandung: PT Reflika Aditama.

Sedarmayanti. 2013. *Reformasi Administarsi Publik Reformasi Birokrasi, dan Kepimpinan Masa Depan*. Bandung: PT Refika Aditama.

Sitorus, H. J., Tanoyob, M., & Irwansyah. (2024). Polarisasi Politik Melalui Interaksi Sosial Di Instagram: Studi Kasus Pemilu 2024 Di Indonesia. *Jurnal Ilmu Komunikasi Dan Media Sosial (JKOMDIS)*, 4(2), 383-394.

Soekanto, Soerjono, 2017, *Sosiologi Suatu Pengantar*, PT. Raja Grafindo Persada, Jakarta.